

1 The role of volatiles exsolution in magma chambers failure

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6 **One fundamental question in volcanology is how magma chambers fail and feed volcanic**
7 **eruptions. For a magma chamber to fail, the overpressure in the chamber must exceed**
8 **the strength of the solid wall rocks. It has been proposed that this overpressure could be**
9 **caused by the strain induced by an increase in the chamber volume due to magma**
10 **degassing. With numerical simulations of volatile exsolution from a growing and**
11 **solidifying magma chamber, we show that the rate of volume increase due to volatile**
12 **exsolution is too low to be the cause of magma chamber failure. Our simulations show**
13 **that water transfer through the mush results in water accumulation at the periphery of**
14 **the chamber. Water-rich layers get trapped in the roof and walls of the body as it**
15 **solidifies; their buoyancy exerts a pressure that can exceed the rock yield strength and**
16 **trigger eruptions. We expect the resulting erupted product to be crystal-rich. Magma**
17 **buoyancy has been evoked as a mechanism to trigger eruption from magma chambers**
18 **that are too large to fail because of magma influx. Our results show that, for a water-**
19 **saturated magma, if volatiles are not continuously lost from the system, their buoyancy**
20 **can be significant larger than the magma buoyancy. Bradyseismic crisis that are not**
21 **followed by eruptions can be explained if volatiles accumulate and the wall rocks fail but**
22 **the resulting fractures do not connect to an eruptible magma chamber.**

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24 How magma chamber walls fracture and volcanic eruptions are triggered is an open question.
25 For a fracture to initiate, the pressure in the magma chamber must exceed the strength of the
26 wall rock. Several mechanisms have been proposed as possible causes of magma chambers
27 failure:

- 28 1. Overpressure due to magma degassing^{1,2};
- 29 2. Overpressure due to magma injection³;
- 30 3. Overpressure due to magma buoyancy⁴.
- 31 4. Deformation of the Earth's surface and fracture propagation from the surface towards
32 the chamber⁵.

33 We used numerical simulations to model water exsolution in an evolving magma chamber and
34 test if the resulting volume increase can cause magma chamber failure (mechanism 1 above).

35 We modelled the growth and solidification of a magma body. In a first stage, the magma body
36 grows incrementally by under-accretion of sills⁶. The successive sills partially or completely
37 crystallise between magma injections depending on the time interval between them. If the
38 magma emplacement rate is high enough for heat advection to counterbalance heat diffusion,
39 a magma chamber builds up⁶. In a second stage, no new magma is injected, and the magma
40 chamber, if present, contracts as its borders crystallise until it is completely solidified.

41 The injected magma contains dissolved water. Water is incompatible and concentrates in the
42 residual melt during crystallisation. When the water concentration in the melt exceeds
43 saturation, it is exsolved and bubbles of supercritical fluid form. In our model, the magma is
44 emplaced at 2 kbar and is saturated with water. We calculated the rate of water exsolution and
45 the corresponding volumes added to the magma body (figure 1).

46 The maximum overpressure ΔP_{max} in a chamber caused by an influx of magma Q_m increases
47 with the wall rock viscosity μ_{wr} and decreases with the chamber volume V_{ch} . For a spherical

48 magma chamber, $\Delta P_{max} = 2 \mu_{wr} Q_m / 3 V_{ch}^3$. In consequences, small magma chambers embedded
49 in cold rocks are more prone to failure following magma replenishment than large magma
50 chambers located in an already heated country rock³. A similar approach can be taken to
51 estimate the maximum overpressure caused by volatiles exsolution by replacing Q_m by Q_w , the
52 rate of volume increase due to water exsolution.

53 For non-spherical magma chambers, the pressure depends on the shape of the chamber and on
54 the compressibility of the magma⁷. The shape of a magma chamber evolves with time as it
55 grows and solidifies. The viscosity of the wall rock decreases with time as temperatures
56 increase. The limit between the magma and wall rock is not sharp but transitional because of
57 temperature and crystallinity gradients. For these reasons, calculating overpressure is not
58 straightforward. Instead, we evaluate the likeliness of an eruption caused by volatile added
59 volumes by comparing water exsolution rates with magma input rates. In the upper crust,
60 magma chambers are most likely fed by dykes^{8,9}. There is a minimum value of magma flux
61 through a dyke below which magma solidifies and cannot be transported. A conservative
62 minimum flux is of the order of $10^{-1} \text{ km}^3/\text{yr}$. It corresponds to the minimum value of magma
63 influx Q_m in the magma chamber¹⁰.

64 The rate of water exsolution is controlled by the magma cooling rate, which itself is
65 controlled by heat diffusion. We find that for an incrementally growing magma chamber that
66 forms by accumulation of sills that are 4 km diameter, the highest volatile exsolution rate for a
67 water-saturated magma (6 wt% at 2 kb) is $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ km}^3/\text{yr}$ (figure 1). This maximum value
68 follows the emplacement of the first sill when the country rocks are still cold and
69 solidification is fast. It stabilizes at $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ km}^3/\text{yr}$ as the whole system become hotter. The rate
70 of volume increase due to water release is several orders of magnitude lower than the
71 minimum rate of volume increase due to magma injection. Thus the overpressure induced by
72 degassing is insignificant in comparison with the overpressure due to the magma influx that

73 builds the chamber. Our results are conservative since we neglected the buffer effect on
74 pressure of water solubility increasing with increasing magma chamber pressure. We argue
75 that if the injection of the magma that contains the volatiles is not able to fracture the wall
76 rock then the volatiles release is not able to fracture it either.

77 The volatile exsolution rate depends on the cooling surface of the magma body, so that longer
78 sills exsolve water at a rate that grows with the square of the sill radius (figure 1). For the
79 volatiles flux to get close to the minimum magma flux, sill radius need to be more than 10 km,
80 i.e. their diameter needs to be about 25 km, which corresponds to the footprint of caldera-
81 forming magma chambers of super-eruption dimensions. However, since the overpressure
82 decreases with the volume of the chamber, large magma chambers are unlikely to fail due to
83 new volume input whether from magma injection or volatile exsolution³. In addition, sill-like
84 magma chambers are more compressible than chambers with lower aspect ratio and are thus
85 less likely to fail⁷. As magma exsolves water, it becomes more compressible, which further
86 limits the overpressure in the chamber.

87 Bubbles suspended in a liquid magma are only a few tens microns in diameter¹¹. Their
88 buoyancy is low and they are quasi-immobile¹². However, in a crystal mush with crystal
89 volume fractions between 0.4 and 0.7, exsolved water is rapidly transported upwards through
90 crystal channels¹². Numerical simulation of this process shows water layers forming within
91 the mush and at the interface between mush and solid (figure 2). In an igneous body that
92 grows by addition of sills, the water accumulates at the top of the sills. If a magma chamber
93 forms, it gets surrounded by a corona of mush, which channels the exsolved volatiles upwards
94 so that layers of water get trapped in the solid roof of the chamber. Our simulations result in
95 an efficient decoupling of volatiles and magmas in agreement with observations of imbalance
96 between the volumes of volatile and magma emitted by volcanoes^{13,14}. They confirm that

97 water exsolution during magma crystallisation can lead to the fragmentation of magma and
98 make it highly buoyant and eruptible ¹⁵.

99 The overpressure required to exceed the magma chamber yield strength and initiate a dyke is
100 10-40 MPa³, although if a crack is already present in the chamber wall, a few MPa suffice to
101 propagate it. The density of supercritical water at a pressure of 2 kbar and at magmatic
102 temperatures (690-950 °C) is in the range of 360-470 kg/m³. For the water buoyancy to exert a
103 pressure of 10 to 40 MPa, with a density difference between wall rocks and water of 2200
104 kg/m³, the height of the water column must be 450 to 2000 m respectively.

105 The simulation does not allow for the water fraction to exceed 0.5 as the material becomes
106 volatile-supported¹². As a result, in the simulation, water-rich layers are separated by water-
107 poorer (less than 0.3 vol fraction) essentially crystalline material. However, the interstitial
108 water in the crystal-rich layer exerts a pressure that is likely to result in a network of micro-
109 fractures, which would connect the water-rich layers^{16,17}. Moreover, temperature gradients
110 coupled with non-linear relationships between temperatures, crystal fractions, and water
111 exsolution are expected to generate pressure gradients possibly causing more fracturing and
112 volatile transport, but those processes are too complex to be accounted for in our model.

113 On Figure 3, we show the added thickness of the water-rich layers with an exsolved water
114 volume fraction of more than 0.3, and the corresponding overpressure due to buoyancy. Water
115 accumulates above the mush, which thickness is maximum on the edge and above the
116 chamber. So, the water thickness varies laterally and in time as the chamber contracts. Mush
117 thickness, water thickness, and buoyancy reach their maximum during the body solidification
118 phase. For an igneous body 2 km in diameter and 2 km in thickness emplaced at a rate of 0.1
119 m/yr, the added water-rich layer thicknesses reach 700 m and the pressure exerted by the
120 exsolved water buoyancy reaches 15 MPa (figure 3). In comparison, the maximum thickness
121 of the magma chamber (melt fraction > 0.5) is 1 km and its buoyancy (assuming a density

122 difference of 400 kg/m^3 with the country rock) is 4 MPa. Provided that water-rich layers
123 connect, their buoyancy would be able to fracture the country rocks and trigger an eruption.

124 We envisage three possible scenarios regarding the role of volatile buoyancy in magma
125 chamber failure and eruption:

- 126 1. The volatiles are continuously lost through the country rock by capillary fracturing; no
127 water-rich layer forms and volatiles play no role in triggering eruptions.
- 128 2. The buoyancy of connected volatile-rich layers fractures the overlying solidified
129 magma and country rock, but either the fractures do not propagate downwards in the
130 magma chamber or there is no eruptible magma available. Indeed, even if the igneous
131 body grows too slowly for a magma chamber to form, layers of volatiles still form at
132 the top of the successive sills (Figure 2b). In this case, only the volatiles are ascending
133 through the crust. This scenario might explain bradyseismic crises that are not
134 followed by an eruption. For example, at Campi Flegrei, unrest between 1982 and
135 1984 characterised by seismic activity and major ground deformation is attributed to
136 the massive release of magmatic gas¹⁸.
- 137 3. Connected water-rich layers form in the chamber's roof and their buoyancy fractures
138 the country rock. The fractures propagate downwards into the magma chamber and
139 trigger an eruption. The mush that surrounds the magma chamber is mobilised by the
140 decompression induced by fracturing and gas ascent¹⁹. This scenario explains the
141 remobilisation of mush without having to invoke reheating by mafic magma
142 injection^{16,20}. If the process remobilises large parts of the roof in addition to the more
143 recently emplaced magma, it also explains the common observations that crystals
144 exhibit a diversity of ages and that the time spent by crystals at high temperature as
145 inferred by element diffusion profiles is short compared to radiogenic ages^{21,22}. Short

146 residence timescales at magmatic temperature are expected from crystals that
147 crystallised in the early, rapidly cooling sills that form the roof of the chamber.

148 In conclusion, our calculations show that the volume changes induced by volatiles
149 exsolution are not fast enough to induce an overpressure that is sufficient to fracture a
150 magma chamber wall rocks and trigger an eruption. However, transport and accumulation
151 of water in the mush surrounding the chamber result in water-rich layers where the
152 magma fragmentation is reached. The pressure due to the volatiles buoyancy can exceed
153 10 MPa and may rupture the country rock if water-rich layers are connected. The volatiles
154 buoyancy exceeds the magma buoyancy so that magma chambers that would be too small
155 to erupt due to magma buoyancy alone can erupt due to volatile buoyancy provided that
156 the volatiles are not continuously released from the igneous body by capillary fracturing.
157 Eruptions are favoured during the solidification of the magma chamber when important
158 volumes of mush are present.

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160 Figure legends

161 Figure 1: Modelled volatile exsolution rate during a magma body growth and solidification.

162 The magma chamber grows over 20,000 yrs by accretion of sills 100 m thick, 2 km in radius,
163 and emplaced every 1000 yrs. The peaks in the curves correspond to sills emplacement.

164 Negative values of rate are due to cooling of the volatiles and a corresponding decrease in
165 their density. The inset shows the maximum exsolution rate as a function of the sills radius.

166 Figure 2: Snapshot of exsolved water volume fraction at time 28 kyr. (a) A magma body grew
167 by addition of sills 100 m thick, 2 km in radius, emplaced every 1000 years over 20 kyr. The
168 colors show exsolved water volume fraction. The contour lines are labelled with melt weight
169 fractions. They show the limit of the mush (0.3) and of the mobile magma (0.5). The mush

170 has been drained of its water. The water accumulates at the mush-solid boundary and become
171 trapped in the solidified granite as crystallization proceeds. (b) Sills of similar dimensions
172 emplaced every 10,000 yrs. No magma chamber form. Water accumulates at the top of the
173 successive sills.

174 Figure 3: Evolution in time of (a) the thicknesses of the magma chamber (> 0.5 weight
175 fraction melt) and the added thickness of the volatile-rich layers (>0.3 vol fraction H_2O) (b)
176 the corresponding buoyancy pressure, (c) the volumes of magma and mush. Sills are 2 km in
177 radius, 100 m in thickness, and emplaced every 1000 yrs. The vertical dashed line shows the
178 end of the body growth.

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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252 Figure 3